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Executive Summary

The scope of this paper is on exposome research in the context of the right to health and how the results of exposome research can contribute to a just society while, at the same time, the methods by which exposome research is performed adhere to applicable legal and ethical standards.

Section 2 outlines exposome research as an approach to health research that aims to move away from approaches which focus on isolating and assessing singular exposures or risk factors, instead taking an integrated approach to the assessment and impact of exposures in their totality and full complexity.

Section 3 defines health and dissects this definition in the right to health care and the right to health protection, the latter being public health. Section 3 further goes on to distinguish public health from the more individually focused 'medicine'. Exposome research is ultimately focused on public health.

Section 4 outlines the context in which exposome research is placed within the confines of this paper, namely how the objectives of exposome research can contribute to a just society. Section 4.3 gives an overview of the themes and issues that play a role in the ethically and legally compliant methods of exposome research.

Section 5 then gives concrete recommendations on the methods of exposome research and how these should foster trust and enhance participant engagement.

Section 6 focuses on a consumer cohort as a concrete example of exposome research and looks at how the ethical and legal challenges were dealt with in this particular use case. The authors also give recommendations on how participant engagement as it is described in the paper could in the future be enhanced in this consumer cohort.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
Definitions and abbreviations	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Understanding exposome research	9
2.1 Objectives: a multidisciplinary approach of exposures in the context of public health	9
2.2 Approach: the exposome and 'omics' approaches to health research	10
2.3 Data contexts: heterogeneity and diversity of data sources	10
3 Exposome in the context of the right to health in Europe	11
3.1 The right to health and health protection	11
3.1.1 What is 'health'	11
3.2 Public health	12
3.3 The right to health dissected	14
3.3.1 Introduction	14
3.3.2 Right to public health	15
4 Ethical and legal challenges of exposome research	16
4.1 General introduction	16
4.2 Exposome research in the context of a just society	17
4.3 Ethically and legally compliant methods of exposome research	19
5 Dealing with the challenges	22
5.1 Participation in exposome research	22
5.2 Research and data governance	23
6 Use case: consumer cohort	25
6.1 Ethical and legal challenges	27
6.1.1 Public-private sphere	27
6.1.2 Consent	28
6.1.3 Data flows	29
6.1.4 Real-world implications and outcomes of the research considerations	29
7 Conclusions	31
7.1 Conclusions and recommendations for exposome research	31
8 References	32
9 Appendix A: ethical and legal themes	33
9.1 Privacy & data protection	33
9.2 Informed consent	33
9.3 Risk of reidentification & sensitivity of data	35
9.4 Data ownership, empowerment & autonomy	36
9.5 Trust & transparency	37
9.6 Distribution of risks, benefits & burdens	38
10 Appendix B: Research and data governance	40
10.1.1 Defining governance	40

10.1.2 Governance as co-governance by non-governmental actors

40

10.1.3 Towards principles of good research co-governance by
research institutions 41

Definitions and abbreviations

DAC	Data Access Committee
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
ELSI	Ethical Legal Social Implications (of biomedical research)
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, accessible interoperable and reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
WHO	World Health Organisation

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective and perspective

The objective of the deliverable is to provide a report about how data from a consenting cohort (meaning where the members of each cohort 'consented' to such use) providing data from consumer receipts may be used for public health (through exposome research), in an ethically and data protection compliant way.

The context of these questions is exposome research. The HEAP project aims to contribute to exposome research in broadly speaking two ways:

- Providing a safe data platform where data can be analysed.
- Case studies of such analyses.

The objective of this deliverable seems most of all linked to the second aspect of the HEAP project.

In that sense, the objective of this Deliverable is relatively concise. Yet, it must be seen in the broader context of exposome research. What does exposome research mean from an ELSI (ethical, legal, social implications of biomedical research) perspective? We started with analysing that question before discussing the more concrete questions.

As we will discuss in the following chapter, exposome research seems to be at the conjunction of various ELSI issues of biomedical research: public health and responsibilities of government to further public health but also possible responsibilities of citizens for their 'own health'; 'big data research' with a vast history of ELSI discussions and sample derived data which means biobanking, with an equally vast fairly recent history of ELSI discussions.¹ The latter discussion overlaps with the big data discussion but with the added element that analysing tissue means -omics research, which amongst other things can generate new data of direct relevance for the participant or his or her next of kin.

The big data discussion has a tendency of trying to find a balance between individual control over data and the impossibility to achieve that fully in big data research which is also subject to the FAIR principles.² The purpose of the big data analysis seems often to get lost in these discussions.

¹ The summary of some of those discussions can be found in the Appendices.

² Vayena & Blasimme, *The Journal of law, medicine & ethics: a journal of the American Society of Law, Medicine & Ethics* 2018/46.

Here we started with the purpose of exposome research which in our opinion is, translated into ELSI terms, the right to health and the closely connected right to health protection. From that perspective we will analyse the big data and -omics analyses inherent to exposome research.

At the same time all research with personal data must comply with certain basic principles as amongst other things laid down in the EU General Data Protection Regulation and national legislation. Yet, from the perspective taken in the Deliverable, that is the inner ring of the discussion.

That perspective is shown in the following picture.

The scheme shows our perspective and guides the more concrete discussions in a way but does not immediately make those discussions easier. The right to health seems in a way, beyond question. But on a global scale, it would require very difficult choices as health is intrinsically linked with economic conditions to sustain a health care system and justice which offers equal access to those possibilities which a country may offer. This would open Pandora's box of profound questions of justice on a global scale.³

We can leave that box closed in a European project as HEAP and can limit the discussion to relatively luxury position of the right to health and health protection in Europe.

2 Understanding exposome research

In order to identify and assess the ethical and legal challenges specific to exposome research, it may be helpful to sketch out in general terms what exposome research *is*.

³ See amongst others N. Daniels, *Just Health, meeting health needs fairly*, Cambridge University Press, 2008

2.1 Objectives: a multidisciplinary approach of exposures in the context of public health

Exposome research involves data-intensive health research focused first of all on understanding the complex associations and patterns between environmental exposure, health and disease. Generically, the exposome can be defined as 'every exposure to which an individual is subjected from conception to death', involving both internal exposures (e.g. metabolism, microbiological) as well as specific external exposures (e.g. radiation, diet) and general external exposures (e.g. socio-economic influences).⁴ Similarly broadly, the exposome will often involve mapping exposures throughout the life course.⁵

This approach to research builds extensively on approaches in epidemiology which are connected to *public health*. Public health has in 1920 been defined as "the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and improving quality of life through organized efforts and informed choices of society, organizations (public and private), communities and individuals".⁶ The EU and its member states, have incorporated this as a fundamental component of their health regulations and policies. For instance, guaranteeing safety of products and access to health care are secured on various levels in the EU, that of the EU, the member states and via treaties of the Council of Europe. We will come back to that in the next chapter.

2.2 Approach: the exposome and 'omics' approaches to health research

In terms of research approach, exposome research is closely associated with the concept of the *genome* and part and parcel of the 'omics revolution'. Similar to other "omics"-research, exposome research aims to move away from approaches which focus on isolating and assessing singular exposures or risk factors, taking an integrated approach to the assessment and impact of exposures in their totality and full complexity. Exposome research involves an exploration of patterns and associations at and between various macroscopic and molecular levels of health, disease, and biology. Exposome research thereby closely integrates with many other kinds of 'omics' research endeavours. For example, exposome

⁴ Wild, *International Journal of Epidemiology* 2012/41.

⁵ 'EXPOSOME – European Exposome Network', www.humanexposome.eu.

⁶ Winslow C-EA (1920) The untilled fields of public health. *Science* 51:23; taken from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_health

research can also encompass microbiomics studies focused on how patterns of health and disease manifest themselves in the human gut, and/or explore how these relate to viral and bacterial exposures in the physical environment. In doing so, exposome research and genome research can also be complementary,⁷ sometimes zooming in on particular kinds of exposures and biological responses.⁸ Also in terms of research techniques, genomics research serves as a model to which exposome research can aspire – as expressed in project titles such as 'the Human Exposome Project'.⁹ Exposome research also employs data-driven, data-intensive methods to generate, analyse and interpret environmental exposure and its impacts on health, with a focus on exploring patterns and statistical associations of health and disease as they are manifested in and mediated by complex processes and chains of events at the molecular and biological levels.

2.3 Data contexts: heterogeneity and diversity of data sources

In turning towards exploratory omics data, human exposome research thereby also involves drawing on and interlinking wide-ranging and novel sources and contexts for sourcing data. This can involve data and biological or microbiological (e.g., stool) samples from persons, but also samples procured from the personal physical environment. Moreover, such data can be collected longitudinally and in diverse contexts. Exposome methods will typically be applied in contexts that are similar to other exposure-related studies. However, taking the full scope of potential exposures into account also means that such exposure assessment will need to reach out and become connected to other contexts and data collected therein. It is hard to characterise the archetypical "exposome study" in this sense: heterogeneity and diversity is key.

3 The exposome in the context of the right to health in Europe

⁷ Vrijheid, *Thorax* 2014/69.

⁸ Vermeulen e.a., *Science* 2020/367.

⁹ 'The Human Exposome Project', <https://humanexposomeproject.com>.

3.1 *The right to health and health protection*

3.1.1 *What is 'health'*

Though this rarely happens,¹⁰ any discussion about the right to health should start with discussing the concept of 'health' first. That concept then proves to be quite complicated or at least not self-evident. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health in its statutes as 'a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, not merely the absence of disease or infirmity'.¹¹ Given that definition, 'health' is unattainable. Ordinary worries of daily life ('didn't I forget my keys', 'is the kettle still on') or more importantly grief because of the loss of a relationship with a next of kin or loved one, would mean that we are unhealthy while in fact, these are natural phases we must go through. These can become unhealthy if they go beyond a certain point which handicaps the person concerned in his or her functioning as that person would see it. And the latter is also dependent on how society will accept temporary 'dysfunction' because of life events which all of us will encounter sooner or later. Moving from the mental aspect of health, people with disabilities or simply growing older with all the limitations – as compared to their younger selves – attached to that, could never be called healthy according to the WHO definition while they still can lead fulfilling lives to their own standards. Building on the works of others¹² and while acknowledging the political impact of the WHO definition, Leonardi recently summarised the critique on this, in his words 'utopian', definition. He proposes 9 features by which in combination health can be defined and, in some ways, measured.¹³

To summarise those and without doing justice to the nuances, these 9 features define health as the capability to cope with and to manage one's own malaise and well-being, while neither reducing health to diseases or infirmities, nor to physical parameters. Health is then constructed as a capability to be healthy, as an ongoing process which is potentially achievable for everyone, under all circumstances. It encompasses both individual and social variables, thereby avoiding purely individualist approaches or purely socially determined visions on health.

¹⁰ Toebes e.a. 2022.

¹¹ Constitution of the World Health Organisation, New York, 22-07-1946.

¹² Huber e.a., *BMJ* 2011/343.

¹³ Leonardi, *International Journal of Health Services* 2018/48.

The main take of Leonardi's essay is that 'health' should at least partially be seen through the eyes of the beholder. When taken seriously, this would have important consequences for public health measures (see section 3.3) but also for the participant facing governance by cohorts (see section 5.2). It would lead to a different perspective. Health research and public health measures should not be guided by an abstract notion, based on the ideal type of someone who lives a healthy life according to magazines like 'Men's or Women's health', but according to what daily ordinary people find valuable, even though that might be called unhealthy according to the 'ideal type'.

3.2 Public health

According to an early definition public health is "the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting health through the organized efforts and informed choices of society, organizations, public and private, communities and individuals".¹⁴ This early definition seems preferable to a more modern one as "Public health is what we, as a society, do collectively to assure the conditions for people to be healthy".¹⁵ Such a definition seems too broad. Assuring is a utopian ambition and still there is public health. When health care is organised collectively as in European countries, that also, if not assures, contributes to many people becoming healthy (again), yet we wouldn't call all health care 'public health'.

Buchanan distinguishes four ways where public health differs from 'medicine'.¹⁶ In our words these can be described as follows, where the fourth row (as we are talking about research in this document) is our addition. We acknowledge that there are grey zones and the more private (first row) and the more public (second row) are intertwined. Yet, as a generic description of the differences between everyday health care for patients and public health this schema is in our opinion very useful. We added another row, the fourth in this scheme, explaining the difference between patient-oriented health research and public health research.

Medicine	Public health
The individual or family	Groups of the population
Treating illness	Prevention

¹⁴ Winslow, *Science* 1920/51.

¹⁵ Health 1988.

¹⁶ David R. Buchanan, p. 290–343 at p. 291-292.

Focus on internal physiological processes	Focusses on interactions between people and their environment (in the broadest sense), not only the physical but also the social.
Research will lead to new professional guidelines (largely an internal debate within medicine, sometimes and even preferably with patient organisations) and sometimes to new standards about which health care is reimbursed by the collective health care system. Only in the case of 'individual findings' ¹⁷ results are fed back to the participants insofar as the data protection techniques used in the research would allow that.	Results will lead to an external, societal, and political debate about prevention (the second row). Researchers can participate in that debate as their research ignited it. But that is not an internal debate. The researchers will contribute more as knowledgeable citizens about the underlying facts than because of their knowledge about the social and sometimes economical trade-offs or the ethical consequences of the possible prevention policies. However, as the methods of exposome research and other health research are in most instances the same, ¹⁸ also 'individual findings' results are fed back to the participants insofar as the data protection techniques used in the research would allow that.
Reliance on professional authority to follow counsel/prescriptions (and within what is reimbursed within the health care system).	Public authority behind collective measures which can range from nudging to coercion.

The latter measures can be aimed at individuals or individuals of a certain group, but each individual must be reached, such as in screening or vaccination campaigns *or* the measures can be aimed at our environment, such as safe water and limitations on compounds in the air. But that distinction is not as clear as it seems. There is an in between area where people which are prone to chronic diseases due to 'unhealthy habits' are targeted. It is an in between area as that targeting results in measures which are generic in their reach, yet do not affect those for whom they are not applicable (e.g., they don't smoke anyhow) but will affect specifically the groups for which they are applicable. Buchanan calls that targeting personal health interventions.

There is considerable ethical debate about personal health interventions. Buchanan's account shows that the debate is not just 'ethical' in the sense of applying moral standards to daily interactions but requires a deeper understanding of political- philosophical theories which can underpin personal health interventions and even might lead to a different route to

¹⁷ Individual research findings, which may be of direct significance for the (future) health of the a particular participant/donor and/or blood relatives.

¹⁸ We lack deeper research, which would probably mean more qualitative orientated research about what people believe and experience to whom PHI (see hereinafter in the text) would be oriented.

public health, namely, to abolish or mitigate differences in social status and income first of all. As these 'class differences' seem most of all related to habits or phenotypes which contribute to health problems in the longer run. We will come back to that in section 4.2.

Buchanan makes an interesting note about connecting with communities possibly affected by personal health interventions. Therefore, though very implicitly, acknowledging that what might be justified by processes which are inherent to democracy (as all the personal health interventions and other public health measures should be based on constitutional democratic decision making) will not always easily align with how certain sub-groups see their position. Obviously, that is inherent in any democracy as well as that those sub-groups have a voice. But in the context of personal health interventions, it might be that those sub-groups have the least voice. Just as economic interest groups which might be affected by generic measures for a safe environment might have a larger voice in the discussion than from a democratic perspective would be warranted.

We will come back to the community perspective in section 5.2. Basically, the participants in research should be seen as a community as well and the governance of the cohort should foster that. Though these communities (the one affected by personal health interventions and the participants) are not necessarily the same and might only partially overlap, it's the best we can do in the research phase. The implementation of policies is in the hands of democratic governments and their governance.

3.3 *The right to health dissected*

3.3.1 *Introduction*

The right to health is laid down in various treaties, such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, but especially the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. However, these international conventions lack justifiability in the sense that individuals can complain about non-adherence to that convention. This is different for the European convention on human rights (ECHR). However, this convention does not regulate the right to health as such. The right to health is subsumed under various articles, most of all article 2¹⁹ and article 8.²⁰ Additionally, the

¹⁹ The right to life.

²⁰ Right to respect for private and family life.

Charter of the EU stipulates that "everyone has the right of access to preventive health care and the right to benefit from medical treatment under the conditions established by national laws and practices".²¹ From the mentioned documents and case law, it follows that the right to health can be distinguished in two aspects:

- Right to health care
- Right to health protection, hence public health

Given the nature of this paper, we concentrate on the latter.

3.3.2 *Right to public health*

On the European level the right to public health is mainly covered by two instruments, being the ECHR, art. 37 of the Charter and article 9 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), article 114 TFEU and article 168 TFEU. These harmonisation efforts, meaning the creation of common standards across the internal market, entails as a base a high level of protection for EU citizens. This means that in these harmonisation policies the EU has done many legislative efforts to protect the environment and humans from many harmful substances. Monitoring compliance with these directives is both a European and national responsibility, typically involving a range of public authorities – from food safety, the regulation of chemical substances and medicines to environment and labour conditions.²²

²¹ Article 35 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

²² Gezondheidsraad 2022, p. 52 See appendix C.

4 Ethical and legal challenges of exposome research

4.1 General introduction

Exposome research faces several ethical and legal challenges. These can generally be headed under two themes:

- a. How can the results of exposome research contribute to a just society?
- b. How can the methods of exposome research respect the rights of the participants whose data and biological samples are being used for that research?

4.2 Exposome research in the context of a just society

In general, the ELSI discussion concentrates on b. However, if we place exposome research in the context of the right to health, questions of justice arise also within the - as mentioned -relatively luxurious position of Europe as there are still many health disparities, both between EU member states as within each member state.²³ So this right to health is not equally divided even when, within a country, access to health care is based on equal access with solidarity based income redistribution schemes running on the background of the health care systems. Research shows that lower income strata generally live shorter and with more morbidity than higher income strata in the last approximately 20 years of their lives.²⁴ Health is dependent on many more factors than access to health care once one needs it.

From the perspective of justice these differences are very difficult to defend. This is not the place to discuss various conceptions of justice as those are discussed on a scholarly level in political philosophy and on a more practical level in the political debate. Yet, for exposome research, the 'justice issue' cannot be completely eschewed. As, when exposome research is indeed about the right to health and health is unequally divided by factors which cannot be easily explained by the results of the natural lottery or random incidents, and we do find that indefensible from a justice point of view, should questions of justice then not also extend to what the research should be aiming for and what research should be prioritised, given that not everything can be done at the same time. Should, for example, exposome research especially be geared towards

²³ Marmot, *The Lancet* 2005/365.

²⁴ <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83780NED/table>

those lesser off groups and be prioritised as such? Or is it acceptable that we gear the research towards what most citizens will profit from (though perhaps each citizen less than a less citizens would profit more via the first option)? It is interesting to note that these two options refer in a way to two strands in political philosophy being a Rawlsian²⁵ like difference principle and 'utilitarianism'.²⁶

Those questions go beyond the phrase 'a fair or equal distribution of risks and benefits' of big data research as pronounced in the ELSI discussion. Such a phrase means little if we don't clarify what fair or equal means.

And to complicate the question even more; what type of outcomes should one aim for beyond fundamental research which unravels basic underlying biological mechanisms? Is it only that people can make their own choices or on the other hand, for governments to make choices which protect health? We may refer here to the previous brief discussion that public health will often involve measures which can be called 'paternalistic'. That might also be the case when government does not curtail choices but 'nudges' into wanted healthy behaviour.²⁷ In between, there will be outcomes of research on which a government might or might not act with such measures. However, those data might empower groups of citizens that government should act or may empower those groups to act. Gay activists promoting 'safe sex' during the AIDS crisis with governments hardly acknowledging that such sex should exist, is an (older) case in point. Without data about routes of transmission of the virus that type of group action would have been impossible while at the same time the epidemiological data about prevalence and incidence of AIDS might be called stigmatising.²⁸ This might be seen as a warning sign that what some, perhaps with all the best intentions, might call discriminatory, might also empower the possibly discriminated group.²⁹ And 'group' is a complex term here. There might be some which focus on the discrimination and others which focus on the empowerment, either individually or when aligning with others as a sub-group. Who should make such decisions? In sum calls for protection by withholding data from research or not performing that research at all, can become paternalistic

²⁵ For a summary, see: Rawls/Kelly 2001.

²⁶ See: Kymlicka 2001, chapter 2.

²⁷ Van Zeben & Kamphorst, *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 2020/11.

²⁸ For the Netherlands these various contradictions have been documented in: MOOIJ 2005.

²⁹ Rose, *Theory, Culture & Society* 2001/18.

as well. They also might run contrary to other important principles of a free society, such as the freedom of research³⁰ and the freedom of press.³¹ None of these freedoms are without limits and the freedom of research is limited by other more preponderant rights especially of the individual subject to interventional (as opposed to observational) research.³² But the argument of possible adverse effects of the outcomes of research due to discrimination³³ of the type which can be upheld in a court,³⁴ is within the European context in principle unfounded. This is due to the 3 tiers of EU systems.

- The first is that social benefits, including but not limited to health care benefits, are solidarity based in the EU. There is no ground for exclusion except for objective criteria of need, such as below a certain income threshold. The objectiveness of those criteria is also subject to the second tier.
- The second tier is EU wide anti-discrimination law, either based on the EU Charter of fundamental rights, EU directives³⁵ or the European Convention of Human Rights and the subsequent decisions of the European Court of Human Rights.³⁶
- The third tier is then national legislation which can fill in certain gaps left by the above such as for private insurance not covered by the first tier. Example given, the Netherlands has since ... the Act on medical examinations in the context of private insurance, such as for a mortgage, or before entering an employment contract. Even genetic testing is in principle prohibited.

This discussion might seem unnecessary for this HEAP deliverable. After all, we should point it down to the ELSI aspects of the consumer receipts. And HEAP is part of the broader EHEN network which has a consortium Equal Life which might address these questions specifically. Within the HEAP context we cannot draft a treatise about the right to health and exposome research as one of the ways to achieve this.

³⁰ Art. 13 Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

³¹ Art. 11 Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

³² See for instance the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine and The Declaration of Geneva.

³³ Staunton e.a., *Frontiers in Genetics* 2022/13.

³⁴ Discrimination in the daily interaction of people is a different issue. However, it would be very hard to find examples where that happened or was exacerbated because of the results of research.

³⁵ Belavusau & Henrard, *German Law Journal* 2019/20.

³⁶ For a general overview see European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights., European Court of Human Rights., & Council of Europe (Strasbourg). 2018.

But perhaps we can draw some very generic lessons from the above which can be taken up in ad b, how the research should be performed.

The main lesson is that when we do not yet know what kind of exposome research should be performed, or at least when it is difficult to make choices about that, we can at least say what research should not be performed, namely research which might exacerbate existing inequalities, and would preferably give the people in lesser health a better position. Secondly, we might want to prioritise research which investigates exposome factors against which people cannot easily defend themselves as the risks brought by those are unknown to us. In the third place, that if the research would inform about possible personal health interventions, then those measures which are the least intrusive should be preferred.

4.3 Ethically and legally compliant methods of exposome research

The methods of exposome research face a number of ethical and legal challenges. As this is mainly observational research, the Oviedo Convention does not apply.³⁷ There are several (non-legally binding) recommendations and Guidelines applicable to observational research and a host of literature on medical research in the big data era. A thematic overview can be found in appendix A.

Many of these challenges relate to *privacy and data protection*. These include in particular questions related to participant rights (i.e., informed consent) and the (re)identification risks associated with large-scale processing of potentially sensitive data.

Challenges relating to the informed consent of cohorts with volunteers³⁸ have to do with the legally required specificity of the consent for data processing. Demanding that the purposes of data processing are fully identified in advance is often not possible for scientific research, let alone exposome research; not all potential purposes of the future use of data can always be anticipated when the data is collected. Broad consent, meaning that consent is given to certain areas of scientific research, is, conversely, criticized for restricting participant autonomy, and may not fall within the scope of consent as defined by the GDPR. It should be noted, however, that the relevant data protection authorities in Germany have

³⁷ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, 1997.

³⁸ For further use of EHR's data there is also the challenge of possible bias because of consent procedures.

agreed to a nationally standardized broad consent for long-term secondary use of health data and biosamples.³⁹

The potential for inadvertent reidentification of exposome data is similar, at least in principle, to that of genomic data; when linking with corresponding datasets in different databases containing de-identified exposome data, re-identification risks of individuals is considered a risk which should be adverted. According to some, this risk cannot be fully adverted.⁴⁰

The challenges relating to privacy and data protection are closely related to *wider ethical and societal challenges relating to trust in and the distribution of risks, benefits and burdens of exposome research*. These risks can be distinguished between risks for the individual participating in the research and for groups of the population in general to whom the outcomes might be applicable. These groups are not necessarily the same. By this is not only meant that the latter will always be a larger group but also that in exposome research the characteristics of the participants might differ from those to whom the outcomes will be applicable.

To mitigate this risk the specific purpose of the research should comply with the principles for prioritising exposome research as discussed in section 5.2 or explain why this cannot be the case. The participants should be made aware of these general principles as part of the governance of the project.

One of the key principles that affects trust in research generally is transparency; controllers should be open and clear towards data subjects when processing personal data. In the current landscape, data is collected from a wide range of contexts and processed across multiple realms, which raises new questions. For participants it can therefore be quite puzzling under whose management the data falls exactly. Public-private collaborations are a contentious topic and can therefore negatively impact trust in the research, see section 5.2 on how to counter this.

As the discussion in 4.2 pointed out, there are differing views on how responsibility towards health should be shaped. We refer to the previous section on how the benefits and burdens can be distributed. If it is desirable to address and prioritise the vulnerabilities and inequalities of certain 'groups' in society, the principles of distributive justice should be

³⁹ Zenker e.a., *Journal of Biomedical Informatics* 2022/131.

⁴⁰ Dupras & Bunnik, *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2021/21.

adhered to. This means that the benefits and burdens of exposome research should be fairly distributed, by considering whether and how each project attempts to address the social benefits, which measures are taken to ensure benefit sharing and equitable access and whether (economically) disadvantaged groups in society benefit most.

In each of these respects, exposome research faces similar challenges as other forms of data-intensive health research. Some of these challenges can come with twists specific to exposome research and its orientation towards public health. The public health orientation of exposome research changes some of the considerations regarding the distribution of risks, benefits and burdens and may lead to certain rights on data protection being interpreted differently. At the same time, the potentially sensitive nature of exposome data may raise considerable privacy challenges in the context of public health research similar to the clinical research context. In some ways epigenomic data may even create additional privacy risks to genomic data; it contains information about past and current exposures (chemicals, pollutants, childhood trauma, lifestyle). This raises questions concerning the responsibility for epigenetic harm, as it concerns exposures which can, in some cases, be considered as determined by wilful acts or behaviours, and can therefore be seen as individual life choices. As touched upon in 4.2, the resulting data might be called 'stigmatizing' and could inform 'paternalistic' health policies. However, restricting the use of such data potentially robs the wider public of knowledge that could have a profound impact on one's health.

5 Dealing with the challenges

How can exposome research deal responsibly with these ethical and legal challenges?

5.1 Participation in exposome research

General ethical principles of health research such as reliability, honesty, respect and accountability also apply to exposome research.⁴¹ This especially means that a fair distribution of the risks, benefits and burdens should be sought.

- The effects of the diversity or homogeneity of a study population should be taken into consideration, as the composition of a study population can lead to the exacerbation of existing inequalities at a later stage.⁴² As an ethical principle, this precedes the stage of consent and wider governance structure. Furthermore, research which targets disadvantaged groups or risks which fall outside the scope of individual responsibility should ideally be prioritised.
- If participation is to be made meaningful for participants, it is important to communicate the wider potential impact of the study when recruiting.

In the context of exposome research, broad consent is ethically justifiable, while it doesn't have the disadvantages of dynamic consent, namely the complicated IT-system, possible consent fatigue and overburdening the participants.⁴³ Broad consent should be clearly linked to the safeguards of good research governance and these links should be made transparent to research participants. The components of broad consent for governance⁴⁴ should therefore be:

- Ethical oversight: an oversight body should be put into place, before the start of the project, and both during and afterwards to monitor data access.
- Ownership & data management: it should be made clear who is in charge of the management, how the data are stored and shared,

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<https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>

⁴² Haga, *Genetics in Medicine* 2010/12.

⁴³ Zenker e.a., *Journal of Biomedical Informatics* 2022/131.

⁴⁴ Boers, Van Delden & Bredenoord, *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2015/15; Lensink e.a., *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2019/19.

which parties have access and what the policies on intellectual property rights are.

- Communication: it should be made clear how it is communicated with participants and what information can be expected.
- Participant engagement: in order to balance the interests of different stakeholders, there should be a framework in place to continually engage with the participants.
- Benefit sharing: policies need to be in place to share the benefits of the research with the wider community. It is inherent to exposome research that measures will eventually be taken by governments, but results of research which show certain risk factors might already be taken up by the participants and the wider community. In order to guarantee this benefit sharing, policies around dissemination of research are extremely important and should ideally be discussed beforehand with the relevant community. It should be noted that the community of participants will not always be the same in exposome research as the community to whom the results will specifically apply.

5.2 Research and data governance

Governance can be defined as a combination of people, processes, agreements and IT technology required to ensure a consistent, legally compliant, ethically justifiable and accountable management of data throughout the entire research lifecycle (for more information on the definition and background of governance, see Appendix B). The elements of good governance can best be captured in a number of principles. These principles clearly overlap and work in tandem, and as such need to be seen as a whole. The following list of principles are based on and build on the principles listed in several publications on governance for research.⁴⁵

- *Recognition of participants as a collective body*

Participants wish to be seen as more than simply carriers of data. Although participants in research may vary in terms of group identity and unity of voice, the lack of cohesiveness shouldn't play a role in whether participants as a group deserve group representation. As such, they are entitled to be consulted and engaged in relevant decision making. To that end, committees or community advisory boards can be organized to

⁴⁵ O'Doherty e.a., *Social Science & Medicine* 2011/73; O'Doherty e.a., *Nature genetics* 2021/53.

provide ongoing public input to, and oversight of, the consortium's management and choices in the direction of the research.

- *Trust*

To foster trust and transparency, the governance framework should clarify how its operations enhance public trustworthiness and the public good. For instance, the mechanisms described above are also means to maintain trust.

It should be noted that the role of commercial parties in research can affect the trust of the participants in the study and society's trust in research more generally. Possible private interests in the study should therefore always be made transparent. Public-private partnerships may offer great benefits to research, as private companies can offer scalability and technical know-how outside the reach of most research institutions. However, vigilance is needed to ensure that the advantages of a company within the private sphere will not convert to a creeping influence within the research sphere.⁴⁶ In order to prevent this, very clear agreements should be made when entering into such collaborations, the essence of which should then be clearly communicated to participants and the wider public.

- *Enabling data access*

Enabling data access not only supports research efficiency, it also forms the underlying justification for health databases. Part of enabling data access means dealing with access control; who is granted access to the data under which circumstances? One way of dealing with this question is installing a Data Access Committee (DAC).⁴⁷ A DAC functions as an independent and interdisciplinary committee that grants access to certain datasets. In determining whether access is granted, a DAC may assess the consistency with the original ethical approval, the quality of the science, potential public benefit and risks which may impact participants.

- *Supporting appropriate data use and mitigating potential harms*

Making data widely available may come with a number of challenges and trade-offs that cannot be directly resolved by laws and regulations. For instance, a trade-off between minimising the risk of reidentification and maximising the utility of the data is inevitable. From a risk-averse standpoint, anonymisation of the data is the most appealing option. This however severely lessens the value of the data for research purposes.

A governance framework would therefore need to have measures in place to support appropriate data use, thereby minimising the possibility of reidentification to an acceptable level, while retaining the usability of the

⁴⁶ Walzer 1984; Sharon, *Ethics and Information Technology* 2021/23.

⁴⁷ See for instance: Murtagh e.a., *Human Genomics* 2018/12.

data. A framework such as the Six Safes⁴⁸, which breaks down data access to a set of six dimensions, is helpful in determining the reidentification risks.

The principle of appropriate data use and mitigation of potential harms could be supplemented with the principle of accountability; meaning that custodians of health databases and biobanks should be accessible and responsive to all stakeholders.

- *Promoting equity in access, use, and analysis*

Data should be reused according to the FAIR principles. Research groups with lesser means should also be able to use the data. A graduated calculation in the costs of using the database could be considered.

⁴⁸ Desai, Ritchie & Welpton 2016; See also: Groos & Veen, *European Data Protection Law Review* 2020/6.

6 Use case: consumer cohort

From our analysis of the public health context of exposome research and the ethical and legal challenges such research generally faces, we turn to the specific focus of this deliverable: how do such issues play out in the specific case of exposome research drawing on consumer receipts data?

6.1 Introduction into the HEAP consumer cohort use case

Statens Serum Institut (SSI), a Danish research institute, has as part of the HEAP project started a consumer cohort, which has the purpose of investigating how consumer food shopping behaviour affects the health of Danes. This research is carried out by the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology and Prevention of SSI.

This research fits well with a general trend where consumer receipts are increasingly seen as a new promising way of health research.⁴⁹

The method of utilizing consumer food shopping behaviour can be advantageous for public health and for research. For instance, they can be used for investigations into food-borne diseases outbreaks.⁵⁰ The method of utilizing consumer food purchase data in investigating outbreaks is an alternative method to the method of patient interviews and surveys. Food-borne disease outbreaks are complex to investigate when the method of patient interviewing is used, because several factors may cause outbreaks that may not emerge in the interviews.⁵¹ Thus the alternative method of using consumer data is helpful as that information is collected and stored in searchable databases. Further, digital receipts are helpful as they can serve as an objective and automatically traceable digital marker for individual food choice behaviour, and do not require consumers to manually log their meals.⁵²

The consumer cohort study focuses on analysing purchase patterns and health information over time. The health information comes from information given by the participants and from the Danish registries (see hereinafter). The Danish consumer cohort is exemplary for how through exposome research more diverse data sets can be used as a way of using

⁴⁹ Wu e.a., *Nutrients* 2022/14.

⁵⁰ Møller, Mølbak & Ethelberg, *Eurosurveillance* 2018/23.

⁵¹ Møller, Mølbak & Ethelberg, *Eurosurveillance* 2018/23, p. 1.

⁵² Wu e.a., *Nutrients* 2022/14.

and learning from data that would otherwise be neglected for health purposes. The aim of the project is that in the long run, new knowledge is found about the impact of our lifestyle on our health. It is carried out by investigating connections between our health and what we consume or are otherwise exposed to throughout our life. The study is considered to be exposome research, as it is a way of understanding the environmental exposures and their consequences. Linking information on shopping habits and information on health and diseases from registries will further this goal.

The data could be used for studies concerning how shopping behaviour affects health on an individual basis or disorders in relatively short periods of time. Examples of the use could be studies of the relationship between what we buy, and the risk of contracting a disease such as salmonella or the exacerbation of diseases such as inflammatory bowel disease or diabetes. It can also be used for studies concerning how shopping behaviour affects the health over longer periods of time; what shopping patterns are seen in people who remain disease and medication free throughout life. Furthermore, the data could give more detailed insight into the lifestyle of Danes.

Data that is collected for the study consists of purchase information, information about the health of the participants (lab results, use of medication, surgeries, and communication with the health care system) and information from public registries about the household environment and any illnesses in the family of the participants.

Additionally, there are data provided in the consent form (e.g., the data subject's wishes in relation to the registration for participation in specific projects and subscription to receive newsletters).

The purchase information of participants is continuously collected from a digital receipts provider. This is a commercial company which provides this service for some time already, although usually outside a research context. Consumers register their payment cards on the company website or in the app and receive digital receipts for the purchases made with the payment cards in the stores that have signed up to the company. The company additionally offers cross channel loyalty programs in which the registered payment card is used as a virtual loyalty card. The app allows the collecting of personal data for the purpose of the register, consisting of purchasing information and consumption habits and the like.

The additional health information is collected through the website www.mineindkob.dk, which was established specifically for the study by SSI, and from national health registers. On the website participants can register for data collection. Here, participants can indicate the state of

their health. This is then used to support the accuracy of information collected from national health registers.

The transfer of purchase information from the company to SSI takes place on the basis of the explicit consent of the participants.⁵³ The data from the health registers may be used on the basis of Section 46.1 of the Health Act. The processing of personal data by SSI is based on article 10 of the Danish Data Protection Act, which states that special categories of personal data may be processed where the processing takes place for the sole purpose of carrying out statistical or scientific studies of significant importance to society and where such processing is necessary in order to carry out these studies. An IT system established by the SSI automates the process of collecting and storing personal data for research purposes. Purchasing data and health data are stored in pseudonymized form.

The various types of data are linked via the civic registration number which in Denmark can be used for a broad range of purposes.

Participants are recruited through various sources; they may become aware of the project by invitation to participate in specific research projects that will appear on the study website, or through invitational letters to participate in studies focusing on specific diseases, where the opt out makes participation in only one study possible.

The results of the research will not be used to support measures or decisions relating to specific natural persons. This includes adjudication, monitoring, or patient treatment. The processing of the data is carried out only for statistical and research purposes.

6.2 Ethical and legal challenges

6.2.1 Public-private sphere

The research takes place within a public-private sphere as a commercial company is involved in the study. This demands attention, as citizens generally tend to dislike sharing their data if it (indirectly) results in financial profit for commercial parties.⁵⁴ On the website, the role of the company is defined in GDPR-terms: the company is itself responsible for the processing of personal data on their website. The company is the data controller for this transfer. The parent company of the participating company is one of the top payment processors in Europe focusing on digital payments and other services such as acquiring agreements,

⁵³ Art. 6.1a and art. 9.2a GDPR.

⁵⁴ Devriendt e.a., *Open Research Europe* 2021/1.

payment terminals, insights and reporting, and further digitalization of payments, which is most likely motivated by the claim that companies can save money that is otherwise put to the use of paper receipts.⁵⁵ Although the company is not involved in funding the research, the trust and willingness of potential participants to participate in the study can be negatively affected by certain perceptions of public health research collaboration with a commercial company or of a dislike of this specific company.

The question is whether this type of collaboration is problematic in this instance. Offering the possibility to share the consumer receipts data directly with SSI without the use of the companies' app is unfeasible. Furthermore, the data are already generated by commercial companies; people sceptical of the public-private collaborations would be unlikely to participate in the first place. The issue of sphere transgressions (private parties gaining influence in public spheres) as mentioned in section 5.3 is in that sense inverted; in this case, it is SSI which takes the leap into a different sphere. The concerns surrounding the issue of sphere transgressions are therefore unlikely to materialise in this particular use case.

6.2.2 Consent

The transfer of purchase information from the company to SSI takes place on the basis of consent of the participants. Examining the wording of the consent in the participant information⁵⁶ makes clear that the consent is formulated in quite a broad manner. Even though the Danish data protection authority has authorised the data processing based on this consent, one may wonder whether the consent has the specificity required by the EDPB.⁵⁷

The consent points out that participants have the option of staying informed about the progress of the research and changes in the project, which makes the given consent more specific over time, and also allows participants to make an informed decision on whether or not to withdraw their consent. This amounts to dynamic opt-out for those who want that. In practice, dynamic opt-out means that participants are continuously kept up to date with the research and are given the option to withdraw their consent at any given time.

⁵⁵ [ECCI0W-reportdigitalreceipts-EN.pdf \(eurocard.com\)](#)

⁵⁶ <https://mineindkob.dk/en-US/registration#1>

⁵⁷ European Data Protection Board 2020.

In conclusion, the consent procedure of the consumer cohort is a broad form of consent. It has certain elements of consent for governance, in that consent is basically granted to the research team to use and analyse the data in an ethically and legally sound way. Information is given on the meaningfulness of the study for participants, the data management, and the benefits of the research for the wider society. However, in the longer run, more participant engagement as described in section 5.2 may be needed to transform the consent procedure to fully realize a model of consent for governance.

6.2.3 Data flows

While the transfer of purchase information from the company to SSI takes place on the basis of the consent of the participants, the processing of the data by SSI has a different legal ground. Additionally, the Danish health registries from which additional health information is collected has yet another legal basis. The challenge is to ensure that participants not only understand this chain of data processing with different legal grounds, but also understand what parts of the processing they consent to. As the data is collected from a variety of sources, it might also not be sufficiently clear to the participants under whose management the combined data falls.

The study website explains these aspects of the data processing in clear language, but for people with no legal background these topics remain complex. This is a challenge that is commonplace for most research studies, and an easy fix is unlikely.

The consent clarifies that FAIR re-use of the data is foreseen. Yet, it does not clarify how decisions about re-use are taken. In order to meet the above criteria of participant engagement this may need to be improved in the future.

6.2.4 Real-world implications and outcomes of the research considerations

The study website currently makes clear that participating in the research can increase our knowledge of how our lifestyle and surroundings affect our health. The study website doesn't give an indication about expectations regarding the real-world application of the study findings. To improve the informed consent process, it could be helpful to describe some examples. One such example could be the already mentioned monitoring of food born outbreaks.⁵⁸

⁵⁸ Møller, Mølbak & Ethelberg, *Eurosurveillance* 2018/23.

There are other applications and possible outcomes which could be more controversial. When it comes to preventing food-borne disease outbreaks, the outcomes of the research can lead to policy recommendations placing more responsibility on public authorities to adhere to their obligations following the right to health. In this case, the research outcomes could be decisive in compelling public authorities to undertake action to protect citizens' health.

More complicated is an example of a study on consumer patterns found that unemployment is associated with increased sugar content in the purchases.⁵⁹ This raises the question, also touched upon in section 4.2, to what extent citizens can bear responsibility for their own health, and whether they should use this information to make informed choices themselves, or that other social policies would be more apt to tackle problematic intake of food containing high amounts of sugar.

Hence this type of research raises the question of how the outcomes of the research could be translated into policy recommendations. Special attention should go to the vulnerabilities and inequalities of the groups associated with, for example, increased sugar content in their purchases. The same case might be made for purchases of ultra-processed foods or other purchases containing high amounts of saturated fat. Considering the potential outcomes of the research, the question is to which extent researchers have the responsibility to clarify the social benefits and to take measures to ensure benefit sharing and equitable access. We assume this to be the case.

The research may also help empower consumers by enabling identification of healthy or climate friendly choices and perhaps change focus from price only (as is the case in most loyalty programs) to more balanced priorities. However, if the participants would be targeted with this information, this would only be acceptable as an option after their consent.

In almost all instances the question remains how such decisions are taken and given the discussion of how exposome research should contribute to a just society, the wider social context and participants' expectations are taken into account. We may refer to our earlier discussion of participant engagement for the proposals of this Deliverable to tackle that question.

⁵⁹ Smed e.a., *Public Health Nutrition* 2018/21.

7 Conclusions

7.1 *Conclusions and recommendations for exposome research*

The scope of this deliverable was on exposome research in the context of the right to health and how the results of exposome research can contribute to a just society.

Section 2 outlined exposome research as an approach to health research that aims to move away from approaches which focus on isolating and assessing singular exposures or risk factors, instead taking an integrated approach to the assessment and impact of exposures in their totality and full complexity. In this way, exposome research not only integrates other kinds of 'omics' research endeavours, but also includes data-driven, data-intensive methods to generate, analyse and interpret environmental exposure and its impacts on health.

In section 3 the authors first attempted to define health. Health was defined in a manner that, while giving objective criteria by which it can be measured, still leaves room for interpretation, where it is recognised that health is at least partially in the eye of the beholder. Health research and public health measures should therefore not be guided by an abstract notion based on an ideal type. The right to health was then dissected in the right to health care and the right to health protection, being public health.

Section 3 further goes on to distinguish public health from the more individually focused 'medicine', and as such focusses on interactions between people and their environment in the broadest sense, which includes not only the physical but also the social dimension. Although there is a grey area, exposome research is ultimately focused on public health.

Section 4 outlines the context in which exposome research is placed within the confines of this deliverable, namely how the objectives of exposome research can contribute to a just society. In that manner, the deliverable moves away from the typical ELSI discussion which is generally focused on how the methods of exposome research can respect the rights of the participants whose data and tissue are being used for research. Section 4.3 gives an overview of the themes and issues that play a role in the ethically and legally compliant methods of exposome research.

Section 5 then gives more concrete recommendations on the methods of exposome research and how these should foster trust and enhance participant engagement. The authors advise a broad form of consent together with participant facing governance. In addition, data security is touched upon, where the 'Six Safes' framework is strongly recommended to determine the reidentification risks and methods of countering these.

It is currently not known how participant engagement is organised in cohorts engaging in exposome research over Europe. To that end, the EHEN project⁶⁰ aims to shed light on that question through an on-line questionnaire to find out how cohorts are addressing consent and participant facing governance in practice.

Regarding the consumer cohort, the authors noticed that this engagement is realised in a rudimentary form. Given the status of the SSI it might be in an excellent position to implement such engagement, perhaps gradually. The results of the participant facing governance survey might be helpful in giving examples what works in practice at other cohorts already.

⁶⁰ <https://www.humanexposome.eu/portfolios/ethics-and-law/>

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9 Appendix A: ethical and legal themes

The following sections of this appendix delve into the ethical and legal challenges of data-driven health research which emerged from the literature research.

9.1 Privacy & data protection

All of the collected literature deemed privacy & data protection to be the most important themes in data driven research. Although privacy (the right to a private life) and data protection are often used interchangeably, data protection can be seen as an additional right which can be distinguished from the right to privacy.⁶¹ Almost all forms of processing of personal data fall under the scope of the right to data protection, while the scope to the right to privacy is more context-sensitive and therefore more narrow.

'Data harms'⁶² can result from a breach of privacy, an unjustified or unauthorised intrusion into a participants personal sphere. Opinions differ on how to categorize or recognise what harm has been done in the case of an unwanted disclosure of personal data. Description of harms can be delineated in both a consequentialist or non-consequentialist manner.⁶³ The consequentialist manner would demand there to be tangible, measurable harm to the data subject, whereas the non-consequentialist manner looks at privacy as an inherent good.

As the themes below illustrate, a balancing act between privacy and other values is inescapable. A zealous approach to privacy will result in less utility, and consequently reduce the possibilities for research.

The challenge for exposome research is ...

9.2 Informed consent

Informed consent means that a data subject should be given all the necessary details of the processing and understand how the processing activity may affect them, therefore being able to make an informed decision whether to consent or not. The concept of informed consent is argued to implement the ideal of informational self-determination, giving

⁶¹ Mostert e.a., *European Journal of Health Law* 2018/25.

⁶² Ballantyne, *Journal of Medical Ethics* 2020/46, p. 290.

⁶³ Cohen & Zultan, *Journal of Medical Ethics* 2021.

data subjects control over 'their' data.⁶⁴ However, there still remains considerable discussion, not only on the concept of informational self-determination,⁶⁵ but also on the level of specificity necessary to consent. This is reflected in the literature, which tends to make a sharp distinction between specific consent and broad consent.⁶⁶ Moreover, there is discussion as to whether consent is always the most desirable option. Specific consent, meaning that the purposes of data processing are as fully defined as possible, is discussed as potentially problematic. Demanding that the purposes of data processing are fully identified is often not possible for scientific research; not all potential purposes of the future use of data can always be anticipated when the data is collected. On the one hand, it is argued that the possibility of obtaining specific consent from thousands of participants for each future study when the cohort is still 'active' may be questionable.⁶⁷ Moreover, specific consent can be problematic given that data driven research is intended by design to reveal unforeseen connections between data points.⁶⁸ Other authors, however, do see the possibility of implementing specific consent options for research settings.⁶⁹

Broad consent, meaning that consent is given to certain areas of scientific research, was, conversely, described as restricting participant autonomy⁷⁰ (and thereby implicitly endorsing the ideal of informational self-determination). Moreover, it is very doubtful that broad consent can fall within the scope of consent as it is defined by the GDPR.

Another issue that was raised concerned consent that has been given [x] number of years ago.⁷¹ This raises a few concerns; first, participants may have forgotten the consent and what they consented to. Secondly, data sets can become more identifiable over time. This casts doubt over whether the consent can still be considered 'informed' many years later.

⁶⁴ Lynskey 2015.

⁶⁵ For a critique of this perspective, see: Finck, *International Data Privacy Law* 2021, afl. ipab017.

⁶⁶ Kalkman e.a., *BMC Medical Ethics* 2019/20.

⁶⁷ Dove, Townend & Knoppers, *The Lancet* 2014/384; Coppen e.a., *European Journal of Public Health* 2015/25.

⁶⁸ Mittelstadt & Floridi, *Science and Engineering Ethics* 2016/22.

⁶⁹ Kaye e.a., *European Journal of Human Genetics* 2015/23.

⁷⁰ Mittelstadt & Floridi, *Science and Engineering Ethics* 2016/22, p. 312.

⁷¹ National Academies Of Sciences, Engineering, And Medicine/Pool & Rusch 2016.

Thirdly, consent may become obsolete in legal, or, more specifically, GDPR terms.

But another perspective is that consent might not be an appropriate basis to protect data subjects' rights.⁷² Mostert et al. argue that consent requirements do not necessarily lead to a reduction in the risks to which individuals are exposed. Relying on consent also has disadvantages to health research as it could disproportionality hinder progress in the research, as it is impractical or impossible to allow data subjects to exercise control over their data in the context of data-intensive health research. This is especially relevant to exposome research.

In addition to the GDPR-centric perspective, another approach to consent emerged in the literature, which is referred to as 'consent for governance.'⁷³ Consent for governance can be seen as a different way of framing consent, in which strong emphasis is placed on ongoing governance obligations in order to protect the interests of participants. Privacy by design, participant engagement and ethical oversight can all be seen as being components of consent for governance. This entails a shift of focus on what kind of information is being provided to research participants. When envisioning consent for governance, during the consent procedure more emphasis is placed on providing data subjects with information on the governance arrangements that are in place instead of all the possible further use of the research data. Consent to governance, however, is more than just a shift of emphasis. It also questions the narrative that an understanding by research participants of what the research entails would provide sufficient protection and sufficiently safeguards the interests of participants. At the heart of informed consent lies the idea that a participant should understand what is being consented to, being able to properly assess the risks concerning the participation. If the information mainly addresses the specificities of data use it may not be very helpful in this assessment. Information on the governance arrangements and obligations, on the other hand, will better identify how the potential risks are being dealt with, as those risks are directly related to how the governance is organised.

⁷² Mostert e.a., *European Journal of Health Law* 2018/25.

⁷³ Boers, Van Delden & Bredenoord, *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2015/15; Lensink e.a., *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2019/19.

9.3 Risk of reidentification & sensitivity of data

Much has been written about the risks concerning genomic information.⁷⁴ The ethical sensitivity and potential reidentifying power of epigenomic data (data concerning chemical changes over or around DNA that do not alter the DNA sequence itself, but do affect gene expression) on the other hand remains largely overlooked. Epigenomic data is especially pertinent for exposome research, as it concerns the effect of environmental factors. Epigenomic data not only shares identifying properties with genomic data, it can also provide sensitive information about data subjects.⁷⁵ Besides being diagnostic, it may also be prognostic.

In some ways epigenomic data possesses privacy risks not seen in genomic data; it contains information about past and current exposures (chemicals, pollutants, childhood trauma, lifestyle). It is therefore not only biology-intrusive, but also life-intrusive.⁷⁶ According to Dupras and Bunnik, this raises questions concerning the responsibility for epigenetic harm, as it concerns exposures which can be, to a certain extent, determined by wilful acts or behaviours, and can therefore be reduced by individual life choices. This, the authors argue, in turn risks promoting a discourse of stigmatization and discrimination against individuals or certain groups.

On the other hand, knowledge on the influence of lifestyle on health is considered to be very valuable, both for individual participants and for public health in general. Furthermore, strengthening public health is not a controversial goal in itself. The question of how to shape public health *policy*, conversely, and which degree of paternalism is bearable, is apt to raise divisions. The issue of responsibility is further explored in 3.6.

9.4 Data ownership, empowerment & autonomy

In essence, questions surrounding data ownership could be boiled down to a simple question: who owns the data? In thinking of data as a commodity, a logical next step would be to view data as falling under the exclusive ownership of data subjects. This, however, takes for granted the idea that 'ownership' is the right framework for capturing the many complicated issues that arise in a data-dominated landscape. Moreover, if data can fall under one's ownership, consideration should be given to the fact that data only becomes meaningful, and therefore valuable, after careful analysis by a research team and in relation to greater [volumes] of

⁷⁴ See for instance: Erlich e.a., *Science (New York, N.Y.)* 2018/362.

⁷⁵ Dupras & Bunnik, *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2021/21, p. 51.

⁷⁶ Dupras & Bunnik, *The American Journal of Bioethics* 2021/21, p. 52.

data. The literature shows that this issue is far from resolved, and there is disagreement on whether exclusive ownership could contribute to a more fair distribution of benefits and burdens.⁷⁷ As some point out, granting data subjects a degree of ownership over their data could create a more proportionate [relation] between the different stakeholders.⁷⁸ Others point out that the vocabulary of ownership runs counter to the ideals of data sharing.⁷⁹

Parallel to the idea of data ownership run the themes of empowerment and autonomy of the data subject. In the literature, it is explained that data subjects' rights (and thus their autonomy) rely on the subjects' awareness and knowledge of what data exists about them, who holds them, what they could mean and how they are being used.⁸⁰ In the context of health research, attention is paid to the data subjects' rights codified in the GDPR, such as the right to erasure, the right of access and the right to rectification.⁸¹

Mittelstadt and Floridi argue that rights of access for data subjects are only meaningful if they can be exercised using a reasonable effort in practice. However, this is hindered by technical and practical barriers.⁸² When it comes to the right to rectification and in a broader sense the right to 'control' data, it is especially unclear how subjects can exercise their rights considering the limited insight on how information about them is interpreted.⁸³ This issue is linked to profiling and surveillance discussed in paragraph 3.7.

Mittelstadt and Floridi discuss the tension between data sharing and data subjects' rights. They point out that there have been attempts to realise data subjects' rights even if the attempts face theoretical and practical difficulties. One example is defining what 'commercial' or 'research' value is when unstructured data would be deleted automatically after some time if there is no longer such a value.⁸⁴ They emphasize that a balance must

⁷⁷ Kalkman e.a., *BMC Medical Ethics* 2019/20, p. 7.

⁷⁸ Riso e.a., *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 2017/13.

⁷⁹ Ballantyne, *Journal of Medical Ethics* 2020/46.

⁸⁰ Mittelstadt, *Ethics and Information Technology* 2017/19, p. 165.

⁸¹ Lamas e.a., *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* 2015/210; Mittelstadt, *Ethics and Information Technology* 2017/19; Ienca e.a., *PLOS ONE* 2018/13.

⁸² Mittelstadt & Floridi, *Science and Engineering Ethics* 2016/22, p. 329.

⁸³ Mittelstadt & Floridi, *Science and Engineering Ethics* 2016/22, p. 330.

⁸⁴ Mittelstadt & Floridi, *Science and Engineering Ethics* 2016/22, p. 330.

be found between realising data subjects' rights and more private, commercial interests.

Regarding ownership of data, there is disagreement on whether exclusive ownership could contribute to a more fair distribution of benefits and burdens.⁸⁵ As some point out, granting data subjects a degree of ownership over their data could create a more proportionate [relation] between the different stakeholders.⁸⁶ Others point out that the vocabulary of ownership runs counter to the ideals of data sharing.⁸⁷

9.5 Trust & transparency

In general, it is argued that society's trust in research is contingent on several factors such as the histories of certain communities and their experiences of marginalization and exploitation with researchers and governments.⁸⁸

When it comes to data processing, one of the key principles that affects trust is transparency; controllers should be open and clear towards data subjects when processing personal data. Transparency was found to be of great importance in the domain of health research.⁸⁹ In the current landscape, data is processed across multiple realms, which raises new questions. Illustrative of this phenomenon is the fact that it is not uncommon for research data to move through cloud environments provided by commercial vendors in third countries with intermediaries. For participants, it can therefore be quite puzzling under whose management the data falls exactly.

If the transparency is lacking, there can be little expectations of trust from participants. Trust plays an important role in the idea of the *social license*, which is argued to be useful to the domain of health data research. Based on society's trust in researchers, researchers are granted moral liberties. In turn, trustworthiness is expected including duties to act in morally

⁸⁵ Kalkman e.a., *BMC Medical Ethics* 2019/20, p. 7.

⁸⁶ Riso e.a., *Life Sciences, Society and Policy* 2017/13.

⁸⁷ Ballantyne, *Journal of Medical Ethics* 2020/46.

⁸⁸ O'Doherty e.a., *Nature genetics* 2021/53.

⁸⁹ Lamas e.a., *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* 2015/210; Ienca e.a., *PLOS ONE* 2018/13.

acceptable ways. Moreover, co-creation of norms by stakeholders and society at large is needed, according to Muller e.a.⁹⁰

Besides trust, other considerations are important for data sharing. Empirical research suggests that the likelihood that sharing will contribute to scientific knowledge relevant to health care, minimal risk of harm, fairness and reciprocity, and trust are all required to develop a sustainable and effective model for data sharing.⁹¹

9.6 Distribution of risks, benefits & burdens

How responsibility should be approached is an important issue in health research. There are different views on to what extent responsibility for an individual's health should be placed solely on the individual. State involvement in citizens' health can be seen as paternalistic if health is assumed to be the responsibility of the individual. From this perspective, state involvement is highly undesirable because it takes away the individuals' autonomy and responsibility for their own health.

According to Verweij and Dawson, the reasoning behind this idea of responsibility is that responsibility is a 'zero-sum game', assuming that when one party assumes responsibility, the other would automatically bear less responsibility. In understanding responsibility as a 'zero-sum game', however, they argue that the inequalities and vulnerabilities of particular groups in society are dismissed. From this perspective, governmental involvement is tolerable for reasons of distributive justice.⁹²

Another understanding of responsibility is forward-looking responsibility, which focuses on the normative reasons to promote and protect health. This way responsibility for health is not seen as a 'zero-sum game', as suggested by Verweij and Dawson. In this view, citizens, governmental authorities, societal organizations and private companies all bear responsibility for health.⁹³

⁹⁰ Muller e.a., *BMC Medical Ethics* 2021/22.

⁹¹ Bull e.a., *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics* 2015/10.

⁹² Verweij & Dawson, *Public Health Ethics* 2019/12, p. 101.

⁹³ Verweij & Dawson, *Public Health Ethics* 2019/12, p. 101.

When it comes to data sharing and data driven research, a widely held view is that principles of distributive justice should be adhered to, meaning that the benefits and burdens of data intensive research are fairly distributed, as found in the systematic review by Kalkman et al.⁹⁴ Benefits to society should be maximised, while harms should be minimised.

In the context of exposome research, the outcomes of the research are beneficial for the participants and the wider public as this increases citizens' knowledge on their health and therefore informs their choices. Responsibility for health can then partially be placed on the individual. In the case that responsibility is solely placed on the individuals, vulnerabilities of certain groups in society might stay under the radar. This might increase the risk for problematic discrimination, if no responsibilities are placed on governmental authorities regarding health intervention. But it is also possible that more responsibility is placed on public authorities to protect public health.

Regarding the distribution of the benefits and burdens, it is important for researchers to consider whether and how each project attempts to address the social benefits, and which measures are taken to ensure benefit sharing and equitable access. To minimize the risk of discrimination, special attention should go to the inequalities and vulnerabilities of particular groups in society.

⁹⁴ Kalkman e.a., *BMC Medical Ethics* 2019/20, p. 7.

10 Appendix B: Research and data governance

The previous sections discussed the ethical and legal challenges researchers may face in data-driven research. Research studies, institutions and data cohorts involved in facilitating and doing exposome research should find ways to deal with these challenges in their governance frameworks. Before going into detail about how they might do so, we will first clarify the meaning of the term governance and discuss main principles of good research data governance.

10.1.1 *Defining governance*

The concept of governance has been developed in political theory as a reaction to changes in political practices.⁹⁵ These changes range from top down control by the nation state to increasing fragmentation of 'steering' or political power by global or regional networks beyond the nation state, the influence of international organisations and non-governmental bodies, and within the nation state, decentralisation, the closer interaction with civil society and citizen's involvement in policymaking.⁹⁶

Many publications when using the term governance are applications of this kind of research agenda; how is a certain issue governed, such as the governance of biomedical research. Yet, there are also more practical definitions, namely about how organisations such as public bodies sets the rules in relation to its subjects. The distinction between the research approach and this more practical approach, can be subsumed as 'governance of' and 'governance by'. With the 'governance by' discussion come normative elements how this should be done, in short increasing legitimacy, efficiency, democracy and accountability.⁹⁷ In 2008 the Council of Europe elaborated on this, with 12 principles for (good) governance by local authorities. The principles include issues such as ethical conduct, responsiveness, rule of law, efficiency and effectiveness, transparency, sound financial management and accountability.⁹⁸

10.1.2 *Governance as co-governance by non-governmental actors*

In the discussion of (good) governance by state actors, the state actors still make the binding decisions though an increasingly complex environment of more horizontal relations with the subjects, agencies and

⁹⁵ Anne Mette Kjaer, *Governance*, Polity Press, p.6.

⁹⁶ David Levi-Faur, *The Oxford Handbook of Governance*, Oxford: Oxford University Press 2012, p. 3.

⁹⁷ Kjaer, p. 11 and following.

⁹⁸ <https://www.coe.int/en/web/good-governance/12-principles>

supervisory authorities, spokespeople of civil society and ultimately sometimes corrected by the judiciary.

Governance by non-state actors will always be bound by the rules set by state actors. It is within the open space left by the regulators that governance by non-state actors can take place. Yet, there might also be a mutual dependency. The better the non-state actors take their role in good governance by, the less necessity there will in principle be for regulators to fill in gaps for (possibly) socially unwanted performance by the non-state actors. Hence, this governance by non-state actors should be seen as co-governance.

Within this open space co-governance is filled in with principles of *good* governance. However, the space is not really so empty. In between state regulations, including international treaties, and research institutions, there is an abundance of non-formally binding recommendations, guidelines, declarations (usually written in capitals) and the like by non-state organisations such as the World Medical Association, CIOMS or international organisations with a hybrid character, such as UNESCO and even the UN. The hybrid character is due to that fact that control of the organisation by the composing governments is limited to the general decision- and treaty-making while many of the organisation's subbranches are filled with other actors and employees which develop their own procedures and have a considerable latitude to follow their own policies and issue their own statements.⁹⁹

In spite of these critical observations, co-governance by research institutions must also navigate through that muddy terrain of quasi-legislation. However, as they are not binding, there is more latitude to deviate if this can be explained and sufficiently justified.

10.1.3 *Towards principles of good research co-governance by research institutions*

The phrase good research governance as governance by research institutions was mentioned by van Veen in 2008¹⁰⁰ which was then also seen as a 'shield' against further regulations or 'paternalistic ethicists'. Good research governance was in this view about principles developed bottom-up by researchers together with patient organisations. Yet, the principles were hardly elaborated upon. The shield insofar as possible did not work and instead, state and quasi legislation has grown.

We are dealing with research data and so it is interesting to look at a definition of data governance. An often used definition reads: *the exercise*

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¹⁰⁰ Van Veen, *European Journal of Cancer* 2008/44.

of authority, control, and shared decision-making (planning, monitoring, and enforcement) over the management of data assets".¹⁰¹

Though 'shared decision-making' reflects an element of good governance by (shared with whom by the way), the definition does not reflect all which can be subsumed under good governance by.

An attempt for an exhaustive list could be as follows:

- Has a clear mission and vision about its function to society;
- Abides to applicable regulations, including of course human rights treaties;
- Takes relevant quasi-legislation into account and has a justification when it would deviate from it;
- Is transparent in the decision-making processes which translates the mission into policies;
- Includes relevant stakeholders in the decision-making;
- Is responsive to the social needs for which the research is ultimately meant;
- Is accountable for its decisions.

But at the same time:

- Is efficient and effective in its operations
- With a sound financial management

In the previous sections (4.1 – 4.7) bioethical literature on research governance was discussed. The collected literature only highlighted a few elements of the general governance discussion and even seems to be unaware of it. The advantage of the review of the general governance discussion is that now we have a framework against which we can measure in a way the bioethical discussion. For example, we did not see efficiency or sound financial management in the latter discussion though those are also essential principles in the broader good governance discussion.

As always with principles, not all can be maximised to the full. Often they have to be balanced against each other in daily practice. The following sections can be seen as an attempt to find such a balance.

¹⁰¹ <https://www.dama.org/cpages/home>

11 Appendix C: diagram of the Health Council of the Netherlands

Bij wet- en regelgeving en beleid rondom stoffen zijn veel instellingen beleidsverantwoordelijk

Europa

Chemische stoffen vallen onder Europese wetgeving die is vastgelegd in de REACH-verordening (*Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and restriction of Chemicals*). Op basis van hiervan moeten chemische stoffen die vanaf een bepaalde hoeveelheid geproduceerd en geïmporteerd worden binnen de Europese Unie worden geregistreerd. Het *European Chemicals Agency* (ECHA) ziet toe op de REACH-verordening en kan beperkingen in het gebruik of een verbod opleggen. Voor de specifieke stofgroepen gewasbeschermingsmiddelen, biociden en geneesmiddelen geldt een toelatingsbeleid. Deze stoffen kunnen alleen op de markt komen als ze zijn beoordeeld en toegelaten door een daarvoor ingestelde instantie. Dit zijn in Nederland het College voor de toelating van gewasbeschermingsmiddelen en biociden (Ctgb) en het College ter Beoordeling van Geneesmiddelen (CBG). Daarnaast worden er in Nederland en de meeste Europese landen grenswaarden voor blootstellingen aan gevaarlijke stoffen op de werkplek afgeleid en wettelijk vastgelegd. In Nederland zijn werkgevers volgens de Arbowet verplicht om maatregelen te nemen om onder de grenswaarde te blijven.

Nederland - nationaal

Nederland - regionaal

De veiligheid van de consument is in belangrijke mate geregeld via de warenwet die van toepassing is op consumentenproducten en voeding. De Nederlandse Voedsel- en Warenautoriteit (NVWA) ziet erop toe dat producenten, importeurs en handelaren de wetgeving op het gebied van product- en voedselveiligheid naleven. Ook kan de NVWA maatregelen nemen als er onaanvaardbare risico's zijn voor de volksgezondheid.

De regelgeving over de fysieke leefomgeving gaat vallen onder de Omgevingswet, die naar verwachting 1 juli 2022 in werking treedt. De bedoeling van die wet is de regels voor ruimtelijke ontwikkeling te vereenvoudigen en samen te voegen. Hij beschrijft wettelijke normen, limieten en streefwaarden voor milieufactoren zoals luchtverontreiniging en geluid.⁸³

= Rol van de betreffende instelling bij beleid rondom stoffen

Figuur 3 Beleidsverantwoordelijke instellingen bij beleid en wet- en regelgeving rondom stoffen